

SYNTHESIS OF POLYPYRROLE-BASED Ga_2O_3 COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Conducting polymers are an exciting new class of electronic materials, which have attracted increasing interest since their discovery in 1977. They have many advantages compared to the non-conducting polymers, which are primarily due to their electronic and optical properties. In this study, Polypyrrole and its composites with Ga_2O_3 were synthesised through a chemical oxidative polymerization technique using FeCl_3 as an oxidizing agent. To examine inorganic incorporation, Ga_2O_3 was introduced into the polymer matrix with different doping concentrations of 2%, 4% and 6%. The adopted method proves to be simple and reproducible for the preparation of Polypyrrole-Gallium oxide composites with controlled compositions, and is suitable for further structural and electrical studies. In this article, the synthesis methodology of the conducting polymer has been briefly discussed.

Keywords: Polypyrrole, Gallium oxide (Ga_2O_3), Chemical oxidative polymerization, FeCl_3 oxidant, Pyrrole polymerization

1. INTRODUCTION

Polymers are macromolecules made up of several monomers, which are repeating subunits. The term "polymer" is derived from the Greek words "poly," which means many, and "meros," which means pieces. Therefore, "polymer" denotes "many parts." Polymers make up the majority of large molecules, or macromolecules [1]. Small molecules known as monomers are the repeating units that make up a polymer. Polymers that conduct electricity as a result of electron delocalization are known as conducting polymers. These substances may exhibit semiconducting metallic conductivity. [2,3] This paper presents a detailed description of the materials used and the experimental procedures followed for the synthesis of Polypyrrole (PPy) and Gallium oxide-Polypyrrole (Ga_2O_3 -PPy) composites. The chemical oxidative polymerization method was employed for the preparation of pure Polypyrrole as well as its composites containing different concentrations of Gallium oxide. This method is preferred due to its simplicity, reproducibility, and ability to produce conducting polymer materials with good yield under mild experimental conditions.

An essential component of polymer nanotechnology is the synthesis of polymer nanocomposites. By incorporating nanometric inorganic compounds, the properties of the polymer are improved, and as a result, it possesses numerous applications. Conducting polymers are ideal for use in electrical and optoelectronic sensing systems due to their large surface area, biocompatibility, and excellent surface tunability. Polypyrrole (PPy),

Polyaniline (PANI), Polythiophene (PTh), Polythiophene (PT), Polyacetylene (PA), Polyparaphenylene (PPP), Polyparavinylyene (PPV), and Polyisothianaphthene (PITN) are examples of conducting nanomaterials that are easily prepared using various polymerization techniques.[4].

Many scientists have been searching for uses for the recently discovered conducting polymers since the late 1970s. These include thin-film transistors[5], polymer light-emitting diodes (LEDs)[6], corrosion resistance[7], electromagnetic shielding[8], sensor technology[9], molecular electronics[10]), supercapacitors[11] , and electrochromic devices[12]. It is possible to create multifunctional molecular structures that open up possibilities for nearly any desired application by carefully selecting the chemical combinations.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Material

Pyrrole monomer was used as the precursor for polymer synthesis. Gallium oxide (Ga_2O_3) was employed as the inorganic semiconductor material for the preparation of composites. Ferric chloride (FeCl_3) was used as the oxidizing agent in the polymerization process. Ethanol served as the solvent for the reaction system, while deionized water was used for washing and purification of the synthesized products. All chemicals were of analytical grade and used without further purification unless otherwise specified.

2.2. Preparation of Pyrrole Solution

A Pyrrole solution was prepared by dissolving 3.4ml pyrrole monomer in 10ml of deionized water. The mixture was stirred continuously on a magnetic stirrer for about 2 hours, to ensure complete dissolution and uniform mixing of the solution. The prepared solution was used as the base for all the doping concentrations.

2.3. Preparation of Ga_2O_3 Doping Compositions

Three different concentrations of Ga_2O_3 were prepared corresponding to 2%, 4%, and 6% doping ratio. The required mass of Ga_2O_3 for each composition was calculated based on the weight percentage of the 3.4 mL pyrrole solution. For the 2% Ga_2O_3 composition, 68 mg of Ga_2O_3 was dissolved in 1 mL of deionized water and stirred thoroughly to obtain a uniform solution. For the 4% Ga_2O_3 composition, 136 mg of Ga_2O_3 was dissolved in 1 mL of deionized water and stirred thoroughly to ensure uniform dispersion. Similarly, for the 6% Ga_2O_3 composition, 204 mg of Ga_2O_3 was dissolved in 1 mL of deionized water and stirred thoroughly to obtain a homogeneous solution.

2.4. Incorporation of Pyrrole Solution in Ga_2O_3 Mixtures

After the preparation of three Ga_2O_3 solutions, the pyrrole solution was added to each in the required ratios. Each mixture was stirred continuously on a magnetic stirrer to ensure uniform interaction of pyrrole monomer with Ga_2O_3 particles.

2.5. Preparation of Ferric chloride Solution

Ferric chloride (FeCl_3) solution was prepared to initiate and facilitate the polymerization and doping process. Approximately 4.055g of FeCl_3 (corresponding to 1M concentration) was dissolved in 10mL of deionized water. The prepared solution was then transferred into a clean burette for controlled, drop wise addition. The FeCl_3 solution was added slowly into each ppy- Ga_2O_3 mixture to ensure a controlled reaction and uniform polymerization.

Fig.1 Synthesis of Pyrrole-gallium oxide composites

2.6. Reaction and Stirring

After the addition of FeCl_3 , the reaction mixtures were kept on a magnetic stirrer for 24 hours. This prolonged stirring ensured complete polymerization of pyrrole, proper incorporation of Ga_2O_3 into the polymer matrix, and uniform doping across all concentrations (2%, 4%, and 6%).

2.7. Washing and Drying of the Samples

After 24 hours of reaction, the mixtures were filtered to separate the solid Ga_2O_3 -Polypyrrole composites. The obtained solids were washed repeatedly with ethanol and deionized water until the filtrate became clear, ensuring the removal of unreacted monomers, excess oxidant, and residual impurities. The purified samples were then dried at room temperature and stored for further characterization.

2.8. Sample Code

For clarity in analysis and characterization, the synthesized samples were coded as follows: P1 represents pure polypyrrole- Ga_2O_3 , S1 corresponds to 2% Ga_2O_3 -doped Polypyrrole, S2 represents 4% Ga_2O_3 -doped Polypyrrole, and S3 denotes 6% Ga_2O_3 -doped Polypyrrole.

2.9. Synthesis of Polypyrrole by Chemical Oxidative Polymerization

Polypyrrole was synthesized via a chemical oxidative polymerization route using FeCl_3 as the oxidizing agent. The entire synthesis was carried out under aqueous conditions to ensure uniform precipitation and controlled polymer growth. Initially, a 1 M aqueous solution of pyrrole was prepared and transferred into a stoppered round-bottom flask. The solution was stirred continuously on a magnetic stirrer for approximately 30 minutes to achieve complete dissolution and a homogeneous reaction medium. Subsequently, a freshly prepared 1 M FeCl_3 solution was added drop wise to the pyrrole solution to initiate polymerization. The slow addition of the oxidizing agent helped regulate the oxidation rate and prevented uncontrolled polymer chain formation. After complete addition, the reaction mixture was stirred continuously for 24 hours. During this period, the solution gradually changed from a light color to a dark gray suspension, indicating the formation of Polypyrrole. Upon completion of the reaction, the product appeared as a dark gray precipitate. The precipitate was collected by

filtration and washed repeatedly with double-distilled water to remove unreacted monomers, oxidant residues, and soluble by-products. The purified material was then dried at room temperature for 24 hours, after which the final polypyrrole product was collected for further analysis and characterization [13].

3. CONCLUSION

In this work, Polypyrrole and Ga₂O₃-Polypyrrole composites were successfully synthesized by the using of chemical oxidative polymerization technique. The polymerization of pyrrole monomer was carried out using FeCl₃ as the oxidizing agent under the controlled aqueous conditions. The different compositions of Ga₂O₃ (2%, 4%, 6%) were doped into polymer matrix to obtain composites at different concentrations.

The synthesis procedure involved the preparation of uniform solutions, controlled addition of the oxidizing agent, and continuous stirring to ensure complete polymerization, followed by purification through filtration and washing. The obtained materials were dried and stored for further characterization studies.

The adopted chemical synthesis proved to be an efficient, simple, and reproducible method for the preparation of Polypyrrole-based composites, making it suitable for further study of their structural, thermal, and electrical properties.

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